

ACTUAL ISSUES OF RELIABILITY RATING AMONG MANAGEMENT SERVICE COMPANIES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the current issues of establishing a trustworthiness rating among management service companies, and provides a classification of the main concepts used in determining the trustworthiness rating of a management company entity. The main components of the housing problem in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the problematic situations of management companies have been identified. The procedure for determining the reliability rating for effective development of management companies is established. In the conclusion, proposals were developed to introduce the practice of determining the reliability of the entities of the management company based on the reliability rating system without the human factor, to provide them with additional incentives and preferences.*

Key words: *housing fund, management companies, reliable business entity, reliability rating of business entity, rating system, EBITA, incentives and preferences.*

Enter. In the conditions of digitization of the economy, effective management of the housing fund and improvement of the quality of communal services related to the social lifestyle and living conditions of the population are among the urgent tasks of the socio-economic state program.

In the development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, on the basis of the programs for the complex socio-economic development of the regions for 2022-2026, the goal is to develop regional development programs every year with a thorough study of the problems and opportunities of all districts and cities [1].

In particular, in 2023, there will be 40 thousand 26 multi-apartment buildings with more than 1.3 million apartments in our republic, which will be served by 787 management companies and 269 housing owners' associations.¹ Based on the decision PQ-5152 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 19, 2021 "On further improvement of the management system of multi-apartment housing" 15 management organizations were selected through an "open competition" in 15 regions of the republic as an experiment and their activities were fully launched. In this case, relevant contracts for the management of 1 thousand 261 multi-apartment houses were concluded.

These operating management companies were assigned the following tasks: management of all multi-apartment housing under the contract, as well as provision of utility and emergency services to single-family houses, organizations (objects) regardless of the form of ownership; beautification and greening of the territory based on the agreement concluded with the relevant hokimiya; 24-hour dispatch and emergency response service. Nevertheless, as of 2023, 1 trillion 213 billion soums will be transferred to management companies and their loans will be frozen for a period of three years, of which 34 billion soums will constitute problem loans.

¹ <https://uza.uz/uz/posts/moliyaviy-nochor-shirkatlar-ikki-yilda-1-ming-47-tadan-10-taga-kamaydi> 449455

The main reason for this is the following problems: the unprofitability of tariffs set for communal services of the housing stock; non-transparency of bills for communal services provided to the housing fund; obsolescence of engineering and communication networks of the housing fund; many companies and management companies do not perform their duties professionally due to lack of personnel. *As a result*, the trust of apartment owners in the company and management companies has been lost. Accounts receivable increased due to incomplete collection of contributions for 1 m² of the housing stock.

Research methodology. Improving the quality of life by providing housing to the largest part of the population is defined as a priority of state policy and is a vector of socio-economic development of regions and the country as a whole. The legal and normative basis is the legislation and regulatory documents in the field of housing fund management, in particular the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 7, 2019 "On the management of multi-apartment buildings" No. O'RQ-581; Resolution No. 64 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 12, 2006 "On further development of private housing owners' associations and the formation of a clear market for residential services"; Decision PQ-5152 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of June 19, 2021 "On further improvement of the management system of multi-apartment housing"; Decisions PQ-292 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 4, 2023 "On measures to implement the tasks set in the open dialogue of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan with entrepreneurs in 2023".

It is important to know the legal aspects of establishing a reliability rating among management service companies, as well as the theoretical basis:

trust management company entity - a management company entity that has a rating of "V" and higher in the reliability rating of the management company entity, while performing the activities of the management company within the framework of the law;

reliability rating of the entity of the management company (hereinafter - reliability rating) - a system for assessing the reliability of the entity of the management company and determining the category based on the rating system;

rating system - a system for assessing the reliability of a business entity and determining its category based on the points given in terms of compliance with certain conditions determined in advance through the automated information resources of tax authorities;

EBITA - is an analytical indicator that shows the amount of profit before interest payments, taxes and depreciation expenses. The level of profitability of legal entities is determined by adding the amount of interest payments, depreciation of fixed assets and intangible assets, calculated profit tax to their net profit, dividing it by the net income from the sale of goods (services) and multiplying by 100 (EBITA margin = $EBITA / \text{income} \times 100\%$).

Economic analysis, statistical grouping, systematic and comparative analysis and other methods were used in the research process. This methodology determines the criteria for assessing the reliability of management service companies whose main activity is related to the provision of reliable management services in the republican stock market.

The reliability rating of the management service company is analyzed on the basis of factors consisting of five main indicators.

1. Financial indicators: adequacy of capital to cover trust management contracts with preservation of transferred funds; financial stability, operational indicators.

2. Business profile: position in the market, opportunities for support from homeowners, business reputation.

3. Business processes: asset and risk management strategy assessment, corporate management quality assessment.

4. Risk management system: identification of different types of risks (hazards) of management service companies and evaluation of productivity of methodologies for managing such risks.

5. Customer service: assessment of the quality and convenience of services provided by the management service company to the management founders. In addition, in order to establish a certain reliability rating, the management service company must comply with the existing requirements of this methodology.

The sum total of each of the above-mentioned five blocks is 100%, and each factor within the block has its own internal unit of measurement. Each factor should have a minimum total score of 1 point and a maximum of 5 points according to its answer options from 1 to 5 points.

Analysis and results. Today, residents are passive and do not want to participate in the management of modern housing stock. In order to avoid further misunderstandings, it is necessary to legally strengthen the existing situation by concluding an agreement with the owners on the management of their shares in the common property. Such an agreement protects management service companies from potential problems. Management service companies will need to solve the existing problems of the company in order to establish a reliability rating and solve this problem. These problems include the company's social problems, financial problems, availability of employees and their professional readiness and abilities, independence and cooperative relations, and other problems.

At the same time, in accordance with the above-mentioned laws and decisions, it is necessary to further strengthen mutual trust between the subjects of management service companies and homeowners, create favorable conditions for them and ensure a healthy competitive environment, and reduce the administrative burden on companies that fully comply with legal requirements. For this, it is important to introduce the following:

- based on the reliability rating, management should introduce the practice of determining the reliability of companies;

- establishing transparent criteria for the formation of the reliability rating of entities of management companies;

- additional incentives for trust management companies and preferences should be given.

It can also be seen from the analysis of the table that the rating symbols differ from each other, usually the most reliable companies are the high rating "A" category. Then, in descending order: "V" and "S" ratings are calculated. The lowest reliability rating, usually indicated by the letter "D", is an indicator of the insolvency of management service companies, that is, bankruptcy or revocation of their license. The above reliability rating scale sums to 100%, and each factor within the block has its own internal unit of measurement. Each factor should have a minimum total score of 1 point and a maximum of 5 points according to its answer options from 1 to 5 points. This practical tool helps management service companies to monitor market developments on a daily basis and show a high degree of adaptability to all changes occurring in the market, as well as help to constantly expand additional competitive advantages through detailed diagnostic results.

Table 1

The scale for determining the reliability rating of management companies²

S/n	Rating type	Description
1.	AAA	- maximum reliability; - lack of attention to changes in legislation, changes in the customer database or the structure of investors.
2.	AA	- very high reliability; - low attention to changes in legislation, changes in the customer database or the composition of investors.
3.	A	- high reliability; - lack of attention to changes in legislation, changes in the customer database or the structure of investors.
4.	BBB	- sufficient reliability; - Sufficient sensitivity to changes in legislation, changes in the customer database or the composition of investors.
5.	BB	- satisfactory reliability; - average sensitivity to changes in legislation, changes in the customer database or the composition of investors.
6.	B	- low reliability; - strong sensitivity to changes in legislation, changes in the customer database or the composition of investors.
7.	CCC	- very low reliability; - very sensitive to changes in legislation, changes in the customer database or the composition of investors.
8.	SD	- unacceptably low productivity; - existence of instructions of the state bank to suspend the activities of management service companies or to limit part of their functions; - mass exodus of customers and consumers.
9.	D	- Bankruptcy or revocation of license.

The analysis of *Table 1* shows that the threshold of points specified in the scale for determining the reliability rating of management companies is determined based on the evaluation criteria of the management companies' activities, the evaluation methodology of the criteria is determined based on the following criteria: the period of implementation of the activities of the management companies, the level of profitability according to EBITA, the positive credit history, land areas and the existence of real estate objects, the ratio of the wage fund per employee by type of economic activity, the submission of tax reports on time, the payment of the estimated tax amount on time, the implementation of the estimated tax amount through a payment order, the use of electronic invoices (EHF) in the legislation the state of formalization within the specified periods, when the goods purchased during the year are realized through electronic invoices, the state of elimination of deficiencies identified as a result of the pre-inspection analysis conducted using the information systems of tax authorities, the change of the location of the account from the

² Compiled by the researcher.

database during the last 12 months, the last 12 months the inability of the head of the enterprise, the lack of trust of the founder or head (owner), voluntary corrections to the submitted tax reports by the taxpayer himself, the status of the special certificate of the value added tax payer, the focus on the recovery of the tax debt at the expense of property, identification of products (goods and services) improper use of codes, provision of employment of persons in the "Iron Register", "Women's Register", "Youth Register" and social register, as well as persons with disabilities, compared to the previous reporting period (received more than the minimum wage) the increase in the number of employees, the average ratio of the monthly calculated tax amount for VAT according to the types of economic activity, the average ratio of the calculated tax amount for the turnover tax according to the types of economic activity.

In conclusion, it can be said that the study of the reliability of entities of management service companies should be accompanied by the analysis of their stability, quality and efficiency. In the theoretical development of management problems, issues of efficiency, reliability and quality were formed in completely independent and different periods, characterized by qualitative differences in the socio-historical situation. In accordance with the above, we propose a practical mechanism for the integral evaluation of the reliability criterion, which plays a very important role as a leading tool for management service companies to continuously monitor the level of competitiveness of the company and make timely clarifications.

It is also necessary to develop a Regulation on the procedure for determining the reliability rating of management service companies. The regulation determines the procedure for determining and maintaining the reliability rating of entities of management service companies based on clear and transparent criteria related to financial and economic activity. The trustworthiness assessment and classification of the subject of management service companies is determined based on the points given in terms of compliance with certain conditions predetermined by the regulation automated information resources.

In order to determine the reliability rating, the existing information about the subject of management service companies is constantly analyzed through an automated system, and their activity is evaluated on the basis of the rating system according to each of the criteria specified in the regulation.

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